

HORIZON-CL5-2023-D3-01-14– GA 101136095

Demonstrating large pit thermal energy storages and improving their components, processes, and procedures for an accelerated realisation of 100% sustainable district heating networks in Europe.

D8.5 Mid-Term Report on Clustering and Cooperation Activities

Document Information	
Due Date:	31 December 2025
Actual Submission Date:	22 January 2026
Type of Deliverable (Report/Data/DEC/Ethics):	Document, report
Dissemination Level (Public/Sensitive)	Public
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Version:	1.0

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1. Executive summary

This mid-term report presents the clustering, cooperation, and stakeholder engagement activities implemented during the first half of the TREASURE project. It provides an overview of collaboration with sister EU-funded projects, participation in project clusters and European platforms, engagement with international initiatives, and structured interaction with satellite initiatives. The report also outlines the mechanisms established to support knowledge exchange, joint dissemination, and coordination, as well as the workshops, events, and surveys carried out to facilitate mutual learning and support the replication and long-term impact of the TREASURE project results.

2. Project Clustering Activities

2.1 Cooperation with sister projects

National and international projects relevant to the scope and objectives of TREASURE were identified at the outset of the project. A dedicated table has been created and is being kept up to date in order to collect data on these related initiatives. Identified related projects include:

- USES4HEAT (Coordinator: KTH Royal Institute of Technology)
- INTERSTORES (Coordinator: Martin Luther University of Halle-Wittenberg)
- IEA ES TCP Task45 (Coordinator: Wim van Helden, AEE INTEC)
- IEA TCP Energy Storage Task41 (Coordinator: Andreas Hauer, ZAE Bayern)
- FLEX_TES (Coordinator: VEKS A/S)
- IEA TCP Solar Heating and Cooling Task68 (Coordinator: Klaus Lichtenegger, BEST)
- Efficient Pit (Coordinator: Solmax Geosynthetics GmbH)
- Integrate 2 (Coordinator: PlanEnergi)
- Push-it (Coordinator: TU Delft)
- Smhyles (Coordinator: Fondazione Bruno Kessler)
- THUNDER (Coordinator: Matteo Porta, RINA Consulting)
- GEOSYN (Coordinator: APRE - Agenzia Per La Promozione Della Ricerca Europea)
- RESTORE (Coordinator: Fundacion Cener)

To facilitate communication and collaboration with these projects and other stakeholders, FENIX and EHP have been designated as the primary contact points, with a dedicated email address (treasure.project.eu@gmail.com) established for this purpose.

In the first half of the implementation period, targeted actions, such as joint calls and informal email conversations, to establish links and initiate cooperation with these initiatives were launched. These efforts aim to enhance the overall impact of the involved projects through promoting structured cross-project and cross-border knowledge exchange, experience sharing, and the organisation of joint dissemination activities, while also laying the foundations for the follow-up exploitation of TREASURE outcomes in later project stages. A dedicated section and social media posts introducing the cross-project cooperation was created on the official website of the TREASURE project

COOPERATION

Are you interested in more energy storage-related news? Our friends at [USES4HEAT](#), [INTERSTORES](#), and [THUNDER](#) share incredible insights on their social media and websites. Follow them to learn more about their great contributions to the field.

And if you want to learn more about our collaborations, check out our [Cooperation](#) page.

FIGURE 1 COOPERATION ACTIVITIES ON THE TREASURE WEBSITE

TREASURE project partners have actively contributed to and co-organised activities and events with the identified projects. Engagement with these projects has focused on gathering feedback, increasing awareness of TREASURE results, and identifying and discussing potential areas for synergy.

As a first concrete example of this collaboration, a joint webinar was organised together with three sister projects - THUNDER, USES4HEAT, and INTERSTORES. Entitled “Optimising Energy Systems: Innovations in Thermal Energy Storage Technologies”, the webinar took place on 26 November 2024. It was organised by the DHC+ Platform at Euroheat & Power, in collaboration with the RHC-ETIP Technology Panel on District Heating and Cooling and Thermal Energy Storage.

The TREASURE project was presented by the project coordinator, Wim van Helden, who outlined the project’s objectives and overall approach. A recording of the webinar has been made available online.

FIGURE 2 FIRST JOINT WEBINAR WITH THE SISTER PROJECTS

TREASURE has also joined a newly established Geo Cluster composed of EU-funded projects. This forward-looking collaboration brings together 11 EU-funded initiatives, each contributing complementary expertise aimed at accelerating the deployment of geothermal and thermal energy solutions for industrial and urban applications across Europe.

The cooperation was formally established on 24 April 2025, when a Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) was signed by the cluster members, establishing a common framework for collaboration, joint dissemination, and mutual learning activities. Cluster activities include the organisation of joint workshops and webinars, coordinated participation in major industry events and conferences, publication of joint insights and studies, and stakeholder engagement through unified communication campaigns. As part of this collaboration, a shared social media campaign has been established, with TREASURE holding administrative rights to manage content and disseminate project developments. Over the period January 2025 – December 2025, the campaign reached 230 followers and generated 8 750 impressions, demonstrating growing visibility and engagement within the geothermal and energy stakeholder community.

The mission of the initiative is to accelerate the uptake of geothermal technologies through strategic cooperation, shared knowledge, and unified outreach, turning research into real-world impact and shaping a more sustainable energy future. The key activities include:

- **Hosting workshops and webinars** to share best practices and technical expertise
- **Engaging stakeholders** across Europe through coordinated outreach campaigns
- **Showcasing innovations** at major industry events and conferences
- **Publishing joint studies and insights** to advance geothermal research and awareness
- **Promoting collaboration opportunities** to strengthen the geothermal community

Information about the cluster can also be found on the dedicated page on the TREASURE’s project website¹.

FIGURE 3 GEO-CLUSTER OFFICIAL BANNER

FIGURE 4 EXAMPLES OF TREASURE NEWS PROMOTED ON GEO-CLUSTER'S LINKEDIN ACCOUNT

¹ <https://www.treasure-project.eu/cooperation>

The first Geo-Cluster Joint Learning Workshop was successfully organised on 21 October 2025, marking an important milestone in cross-project collaboration within the European geothermal community. The workshop, entitled “Sustainable Heating and Cooling Solutions for Industries and District Heating”, brought together a wide range of stakeholders for an interactive exchange of knowledge and best practices. The event gathered more than 100 participants and featured a three-hour programme of expert presentations and discussions. In total, 12 speakers representing 11 EU-funded projects presented recent developments and innovations in the fields of geothermal energy, thermal energy storage, and advanced heat pump technologies. The TREASURE project was featured in the opening presentation, promoting the Geo Cluster, its objectives, and the collaborative goals of the participating projects.

FIGURE 5 THE FIRST GEO-CLUSTER JOINT LEARNING WORKSHOP

In addition to collaboration with related EU-funded projects, the TREASURE project has established strategic cooperation with major European platforms to further strengthen its dissemination, stakeholder engagement, and impact.

TREASURE has initiated collaboration with RHC-ETIP² (European Technology and Innovation Platform on Renewable Heating and Cooling). RHC-ETIP brings together a broad range of stakeholders from the biomass, geothermal, solar thermal, heat pump, district heating and cooling, and thermal energy storage sectors. The platform supports the development of a shared strategic vision to accelerate the uptake of renewable heating and cooling technologies across Europe and to facilitate the gradual phase-out of fossil fuels in these sectors.

² <https://www.rhc-platform.org/project/treasure-demonstrating-large-pit-thermal-energy-storages/>

Furthermore, TREASURE has established an official presence on BUILD UP³, a portal launched by the European Commission in 2009. BUILD UP serves as a leading reference platform for energy efficiency and renewable energy in the European building sector, connecting professionals and organisations and fostering the exchange of knowledge, best practices, and practical tools. Through its presence on BUILD UP, TREASURE enhances the visibility of its activities and results, contributes to knowledge sharing within the community, and supports the advancement of sustainable and energy-efficient building practices across Europe.

Moreover, the TREASURE project was presented at two major industry events: the Euroheat & Power Congress⁴, held in Prague in June 2025, and the Energy Global Storage Conference⁵, held in Brussels in October 2025. At both events, TREASURE was showcased through a dedicated booth, providing visibility for the project's objectives, activities, and expected outcomes to a broad audience of industry stakeholders.

FIGURE 6 TREASURE AT SECTORAL EVENTS

Following these events, contact details were exchanged with representatives from several private companies, enabling follow-up discussions and the identification of initial collaboration opportunities. These interactions directly support the project's collaboration and exploitation objectives and contribute to strengthening links between TREASURE and relevant industrial stakeholders.

Looking ahead, plans are in place to actively explore further synergies with related projects. This includes joint policy events, webinars, and, whenever relevant joint contributions to policy recommendations (notably within Task 7.3).

³ <https://build-up.ec.europa.eu/en/home>

⁴ <https://ehpcongress.org/>

⁵ <https://energystorageeurope.eu/easeevents/energy-storage-global-conference/>

2.2 Collaboration with IEA’s Energy Storage Technology Collaboration Programme

An indirect collaboration with the IEA Energy Storage Technology Collaboration Programme has been initiated through consortium partners who are part of both the TREASURE project, as well as the IEA-ES Task 45. This cooperation supports bi-directional exchange with the aim of facilitating integrated research, development, implementation, and system integration of Pit Thermal Energy Storage (PTES) and energy storage technologies more broadly.

IEA-ES Task 45 aims to provide the knowledge base and methodological framework required to accelerate the market uptake of Large Thermal Energy Storage (LTES) technologies, including PTES, Borehole Thermal Energy Storage (BTES), Tank Thermal Energy Storage (TTES), and Aquifer Thermal Energy Storage (ATES). This project follows the structure of the IEA Task which is divided into 4 Work Packages, as shown below.

- WP1 develops reliable pre-design tools using numerical simulations for LTES optimization, and is closely connected with WP2, WP3, and WP4 of the Treasure project
- WP2 builds a material property database and tests effects of temperature and moisture on performance and lifespan, with connections to WP3 of the Treasure project
- WP3 creates and adapts standards for design, testing, and operation with performance checks for market adoption, and is particularly connected to WP2, WP3, WP4 and WP5 of the Treasure project
- WP4 shares developments and results on improved LTES concepts with target audiences, and interacts with all Treasure work packages and activities

FIGURE 7 WORK PACKAGE STRUCTURE OF IEA-ES TASK 45

Specifically to the dissemination activities of Task 45, TREASURE project partners were invited to actively participate in a series of online sessions organised under IEA-ES Task 45, coordinated by PlanEnergi and AEE INTEC. A first webinar took place online on 10 June 2025. This webinar explored the diverse planning, regulatory, societal, and financial aspects involved in implementing LTES systems, drawing on real-world examples involving Aquifer, Borehole, and Pit Thermal Energy Storage technologies. Participants gained insights into stakeholder engagement strategies, public perception challenges, the European regulatory landscape, and innovative financing models that support the deployment of these energy storage solutions. Experts involved in the Treasure project contributed to the webinar by delivering presentations on various topics, including a PTES study case (PlanEnergi), the European Framework for LTES projects (Hamburg Institut), the stakeholder engagement and public perception in an LTES project (Fenix TNT), and some financing methods for LTES projects (PlanEnergi).

FIGURE 8 PROGRAM OF THE 1ST WEBINAR BY IEA-ES TASK 45

Two follow-up Q&A sessions were held to address questions raised during and after the first webinar. PTES experts from PlanEnergi, Aalborg CSP, Solites, Solid, Hamburg Institut, and DTU actively contributed to these discussions.

The first one took place online on 30 September 2025. Experts were gathered to answer a dozen of the questions submitted in advance, covering three key thematic areas:

- Planning, legal, and societal aspects of LTES implementation;
- Technical aspects, including feasibility assessment, system design, tendering, and monitoring; and
- Practical experiences from real-world LTES projects.

FIGURE 9 1ST Q&A SESSION BY IEA-ES TASK 45

A second Q&A session was held on 27 November 2025 and brought together LTES experts to address questions related to:

- EU regulatory frameworks for LTES projects;
- Legal and permitting aspects;
- Market potential of LTES technologies;
- Economic considerations; and
- System integration and technical performance.

A second webinar was organised on 16 December 2025. The webinar provided a technical overview of LTES projects, focusing on their main phases such as feasibility, design, implementation, and monitoring. It included practical insights from projects across Europe, including the BTES project in Emmaboda (SE), the 56'000 m³ TTES in Berlin (DE), the 70'000 m³ PTES in Høje Taastrup (DK), and the ATES system in Middenmeer (NL). In addition to technical considerations, the webinar addressed the economic aspects relevant to the deployment and operation of LTES technologies. PlanEnergi contributed as organizer and as presenter of the satellite project in Høje Taastrup in Denmark.

FIGURE 10 PROGRAM OF THE 2NDWEBINAR BY IEA-ES TASK 45

As part of the IEA-ES Task 45 project, two additional webinars and up to eight Q&A sessions will be organized throughout 2026 and 2027, according to the schedule below. The third webinar will focus on practical experiences with LTES and provide insights into economic aspects. The fourth and final webinar will present the outcomes of the IEA-ES Task 45 studies and activities. The Q&A sessions will be held to address participants’ questions and foster discussion.

Year	2025												2026												2027												
Month	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	
Webinar						1						2							3					4													
Q&A Session						✓				1.1	2.1	✓	2.2	2.3				3.1	3.2	3.3		4.1	4.2	4.3	4.4												

FIGURE 11 1ST Q&A SESSION BY IEA-ES TASK 45 & WEBINAR

3. Cooperation with Satellite Initiatives

Another key objective of the TREASURE project is to establish structured cooperation with satellite initiatives operating at different stages of implementation, while simultaneously facilitating knowledge exchange and

collaboration among the initiatives themselves. By systematically integrating the experiences, challenges, and needs of the satellite initiatives, TREASURE aims to contribute to the development of a roadmap supporting the wide-scale replication and long-term sustainability of the project's results.

In total, 17 satellite initiatives have been identified, and formal Letters of Intent have been sent to all of them, thereby establishing a framework for continuous coordination and collaboration. The identified satellite initiatives include:

- Roskilde: VEKS
- Eisenstadt: Riebenbauer GmbH
- Weitendorf project (Coordination entity: Waermespeicher Weitendorf GmbH)
- Graefelfing project (Coordination entity: Community of Gräefelfing)
- Konskie project (Coordination entity: PEC Sp. Z o.o.)
- Pristina project (Coordination entity: CES Clean Energy Solutions GesmbH)
- Occitanie project (Coordination entity: NewHeat)
- Ile de France project (Coordination entity: NewHeat)
- Centre-Val de Loire project (Coordination entity: NewHeat)
- Nouvelle-Aquitaine project (Coordination entity: NewHeat)
- Centre-Val de Loire project (Coordination entity: NewHeat)
- Grand Est project (Coordination entity: NewHeat)
- Hanggin Banner project (Coordination entity: Inner Mongolia Longyuan New Energy Co. Ltd)
- Heibei project (Coordination entity: Inst. El. Eng. of Chinese Academy of Sciences)
- Beijing project (Coordination entity: Tsinghua University)
- Odense project (Coordination entity: Fjernvarme Fyn)
- Hjørring project (Coordination entity: Hjørring Varmeforsyning)

To ensure continuous and targeted interaction and to foster sustained engagement and mutual learning between TREASURE and the satellite initiatives, two out of the four planned annual workshops have been organised during the first half of the project. These workshops serve as dedicated platforms for exchanging lessons learned, transferring knowledge, jointly addressing critical challenges, and enabling TREASURE to refine its objectives in line with the evolving needs of the broader stakeholder ecosystem.

The first annual workshop was held online on 9 December 2024. It provided a valuable opportunity for participating initiatives to share insights, exchange experiences, and discuss effective solutions to key challenges related to Pumped Thermal Energy Storage (PTES) deployment. The workshop agenda included:

- Opening remarks and introductions – John Kapetanakis (EHP), Task Leader
- Presentation of TREASURE project objectives and work packages – Wim Van Helden (AEE INTEC), Project Coordinator

- Pitch presentations by satellite initiatives – Representatives of satellite initiatives
- Open discussion on project characteristics, parameters, and implementation frameworks, including obstacles, solutions, and experiences related to social acceptance

The event successfully brought together 27 participants, facilitating productive dialogue among the diverse stakeholders.

FIGURE 12 PREPARATIONS FOR THE 1ST WORKSHOP WITH SATELLITE INITIATIVES

The second workshop was organised online on 16 January 2026 and followed a structured agenda comprising:

1. Opening remarks (5 minutes) – Laura Junasova (EHP)
2. Updates from the TREASURE project, including:
 - Brief presentation of three TREASURE reports on the integration of Large Thermal Energy Storage (LTES) in district heating (10 minutes) – Carles Ribas Tugores (AEE INTEC)
 - Presentation of Deliverable D2.1 on screening of locations and pre-feasibility studies (10 minutes) – Per Alex Sørensen (PlanEnergi)
3. Presentation of PTES implementation challenges identified within TREASURE, focusing on site selection and storage value underestimation (10 minutes) – PlanEnergi
4. Open discussion on the identified challenges (25 minutes) – All participants

FIGURE 13 2ND WORKSHOP WITH SATELLITE INITIATIVES

This online workshop gathered 11 participants (Laura Junasová (Euroheat & Power), Wim van Helden (AEE INTEC), Per Alex Sørensen (PlanEnergi), Carles Ribas Tugores (AEE INTEC), Jan Hagenau (Fjernvarme Fyn), Robert Hvelplund (Fjernvarme Fyn), Olav Flach (Fjernvarme Fyn), Felix Eckert (CES Clean Energy Solutions GesmbH), Simon Høegh (VEKS), Guofeng Yuan (Tsinghua University), Lin Fu (Tsinghua University)).

Apart from presenting updates from the TREASURE project to the participants, this workshop aimed to exchange experiences from large-scale PTES projects, reflect on site selection and land-use issues, and address the frequent underestimation of the economic value of thermal storage. The workshop provided a platform for dialogue between European and international experts on innovative PTES concepts and operational strategies.

The workshop concluded that PTES is technically mature and economically competitive at large scale, particularly when integrated into broader energy system flexibility concepts. Site availability and planning constraints remain key barriers, although innovative land-reuse concepts offer promising solutions. The value of PTES is frequently underestimated due to narrow feasibility assumptions that exclude electricity-sector services, cooling integration and future energy price developments. Experience from China demonstrated the potential for combining heating, cooling and urban land reuse within large-scale PTES projects.

The third annual workshop is tentatively scheduled for December 2026, with the exact date to be confirmed at a later stage.

In addition to the workshops, a targeted survey is currently being conducted as a proactive measure to better understand and address the specific needs of the satellite initiatives. The survey focuses on gathering insights relevant to PTES planning and implementation guidelines and was distributed to all satellite partners. Several responses have already been received, and the feedback collected will be used to inform the development of practical guidelines and tailored support measures within the project.

Survey on Large Thermal Energy Storage in District Heating Systems

This survey explores the economic viability, payback periods, resilience, and non-market benefits of large thermal energy storage in district heating systems.

Your input is highly appreciated and will contribute to advancing energy storage solutions for a more sustainable future.

🕒 The survey takes **only 3 minutes** and your answers will be treated anonymously.

This survey has been developed within the framework of the TREASURE project.

About the project: The TREASURE project is funded by the European Union under Grant Agreement No. 101136095. The project aims to bridge the gap between research and practice in the field of thermal energy storage. More information: www.treasure-project.eu

FIGURE 14 SURVEY ON LTES IN DH SYSTEMS

4. Conclusion

The clustering and cooperation activities presented in this report demonstrate that TREASURE has successfully established itself as an active and well-connected actor within the European and international thermal energy storage landscape. Through systematic engagement with sister projects, European platforms, international initiatives, and satellite projects, TREASURE has created a strong framework for bi-directional knowledge exchange, mutual learning, and coordinated dissemination.

The combination of joint events, cluster-based collaboration, participation in international expert forums, and structured interaction with satellite initiatives has significantly enhanced the project's visibility and relevance beyond the consortium. These activities have not only supported dissemination objectives but have also generated concrete feedback, identified common implementation challenges, and highlighted opportunities for alignment and replication across different contexts.

Looking ahead, the established cooperation mechanisms provide a solid foundation for continued engagement in the second half of the project. Planned follow-up workshops, expanded collaboration with related initiatives, and the integration of feedback from satellite projects will further support the development of robust roadmaps, policy-relevant recommendations, and exploitation pathways.

Overall, the clustering and collaboration activities are expected to play a key role in ensuring the long-term impact, scalability, and sustainability of TREASURE project outcomes.

